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THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON HIGHER EDUCATION – ARE BLENDED LEARNING FORMATS THE WAY FORWARD?

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ABSTRACT

Higher education institutes all over the world have rapidly adopted emergency remote teaching in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This shift has been analysed by numerous publications and from various angles. The state-of-the-art literature spans from descriptive analyses, which provide overviews on which tools or Learning Management Systems (LMS) were most frequently used, to more complex analyses that focus on the perception of technology adoption. The pedagogical field is urgently trying to understand and leverage the advantages and mitigate the drawbacks of e-learning to transition to post-pandemic scenarios. An early consensual lesson learned

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seems to be that presence learning cannot be fully compensated with digital formats, thus hybrid/blended learning formats seem to be the way forward. Yet, comprehensive insights into whether European higher education institutes intend to permanently incorporate the didactic shift to more digital formats post-pandemic are currently missing. Here, we present a review of 42 publications on digital learning during the COVID-19 pandemic and derive hypotheses regarding the future implementation of blended learning formats. This literature review will serve as the methodological foundation for the pedagogical studies planned within the ide3a project (<https://ide3a.net>). We plan to complement this effort with a Europe-wide survey among higher education institutes to identify best practices in digital synchronous and asynchronous, as well as hybrid/blended learning formats for international and interdisciplinary settings. ide3a will then provide the environment for testing some of these formats, as well as hypotheses related to the identified best practices.

1 INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced a rapid global shift to emergency remote teaching from March 2020 onward. At the time of writing, more than one year after the start of the pandemic, education is still largely remote. Various scientific and technical publications have analysed this abrupt shift to remote teaching and delivered first conclusions regarding its success and the overall impact of COVID-19 on higher education. This work presents the findings of a literature review aimed at identifying current trends, open challenges, and priority research questions to be investigated within the ide3a project (<https://ide3a.net>). As a project funded by the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD), ide3a aims to test and establish blended learning formats within an international and multidisciplinary consortium of partner universities. The literature review presented here was conducted to formulate lessons learned during the pandemic in terms of pedagogic added value, or hindrances to take into account for future blended learning formats.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review described here was conducted using the Technische Universität Berlin's (TUB) library search engine 'Primo' (<https://tu-berlin.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com>). Primo searches across the TUB's and Berlin University of Arts' collections, covering several hundred million articles and e-books, which are published by Springer, EBSCO, Wiley and ACS, among other academic publishers. The search was carried out in February 2021, which is why this review only includes publications up to mid-February. The search terms used were ("E-learning" OR "Remote learning" OR "Digital education" OR "Digital learning" OR "Online learning" OR "Distance learning") AND ("COVID-19" OR "Corona" OR "Sars-Cov-2" OR "Pandemic" OR "Crisis") AND ("Higher Education" OR "Tertiary education" OR "University OR Universities"). The search initially returned 12,999 results. These were filtered by publication date to fit the COVID-19 pandemic time span (2020-2021), by format (scientific peer-reviewed journals) to exclude newspapers or other non peer-reviewed formats, and key terms (Distance Learning, Education, Education & Educational Research, Learning, Higher Education). After filtering, the search returned 1,315 results. These were then further filtered based on their relevance as indicated by their title. Exclusion criteria were (i) 'Too sectoral (e.g., Dental Education)', (ii) 'Research on COVID-19 itself', (iii) 'Policy or practice suggestions during COVID-19', (iv) 'Mental Health effects of COVID-19 or the pandemic', or (v) 'Explicit focus on the first weeks of emergency remote teaching'. Fifty-one publications remained afterwards for review. During the review of these 51 publications, another 9 had to be excluded upon reading, as they turned out to be opinion, single page conference papers, data articles, or concentrated on secondary education. The final number of articles reviewed was 42 and their metadata are available in an open-access repository [1].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Literature Review Outcome

3.1.1 Descriptive overview of review results

The remaining 42 publications were first categorised chronologically, according to their submission date. As can be observed in Figure 1, the majority of the publications reviewed was submitted before October 2020. It is likely that, at the time of writing, some of the publications submitted during the ‘late stage pandemic’ were still under review and not yet published. Otherwise, the contributions appear quite balanced, with only the student perspective articles slightly increasing during the ‘mid stage’.

Fig. 1. Overview of literature review outcome. Note: The reviewed publications are categorised according to their submission date. Marker size and color are proportional to the number of papers in each category, indicated also by the label in each circle. Pandemic stages were determined by the global case number trend.

Regarding methodology and format, the majority of articles made use of surveys (50%), followed by experience reports (26%), interviews (9.5%), documentary analysis (9.5%) and literature reviews (5%). Characterised by their methodology, early stage publications concentrated more on qualitative analyses, with 66% of publications relying on experience reports, interviews, and documentary analyses, while this is the case for only 40% in mid and late stage publications. The use of surveys doubled from early stage (30%) to mid (60%) and late (60%) stage publications [1]. Despite filtering for explicit niche focus, it can be said that analyses of COVID-19 impact on higher education were still quite sectoral, with almost 50% of all reviewed articles concentrating on one sector or broader study field; 40% of these sectoral analyses focused on the medical or health services education sector. Additionally, 26% of articles were single-university studies. Although several articles also conducted multi-university surveys, there has only been one global study (n=30,383 participants) to date by Aristovnik et al. [2], concentrating on student perception.

3.1.2 Emerging conclusions

E-learning is not the same as emergency remote teaching, which became clear even in articles where authors used the terms interchangeably. As pointed out by 28%

(n=12 publications), the emergency response did not contain the same level of pedagogical planning and theory that e-learning usually should, and which would be required to ensure similar perceived success of the format compared to face-to-face teaching. Various tools were used to simply 'move' traditional formats online, making synchronous (live) remote lectures the most often used format (59.4%), followed by asynchronous formats (35.9%) such as sending presentations, video recordings, and written chat or forum communication. The remaining 4.7% were audio recordings [2]. The acceptance and intention to use tools such as these and digital pedagogy during the pandemic has been evaluated by several psychometric analyses using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), a model used to statistically identify psychological determinants of acceptance of information technology. The main predictor for acceptance and intention to use remote teaching was perceived usefulness, which for students was most strongly moderated by enjoyment [3]. In order for emergency remote teaching to be similarly effective and accepted compared to face-to-face teaching and e-learning, adaptations in the delivery of digital formats are therefore necessary.

The rapidness of the shift exposed large gaps in digital readiness and existing underlying issues, which explain the improvisational nature of the emergency response. 40% (n=17) of the reviewed articles pointed to the fact that instructors were lacking digital competences to execute proper e-learning, and additionally, in most cases received little structural or institutional support in acquiring these skills [1]. Many authors were also stern in pointing to underlying issues with their respective educational systems, which were highlighted by the pandemic. Legislative hinderances surrounding data privacy and e-learning in general are halting the digital transformation underway in Germany and Italy for example, silo-thinking and rigidity in schedules and curricula have created an often stressful experience for students, and access to higher education is still limited by the physical capacity of universities. Higher education institutes in developing countries are faced with the additional challenge of unreliable or expensive access to critical infrastructure, including electricity and cost of data bundles, pointing to missing investments on larger scales. Due to this confrontational experience, 47% (n=20) of reviewed articles saw the current emergency remote response as a chance for pedagogical improvement [1].

Levering the benefits of digital education formats could lead to a didactic paradigm shift after the pandemic. It is evident that the current state of emergency remote teaching is not going to remain the educational model after the pandemic. Yet, several articles indicated that some of the benefits experienced, especially related to the flexibility remote education can bring to the educational sector, should be retained. Some even directly voiced the wish to continue using digital or hybrid formats [4]. Blended learning therefore seems to be the way forward, both for enabling education during the eventual final phases of the pandemic and afterwards. 40% of reviewed articles (n=17) pointed to possible lasting effects or necessary shifts in didactic thinking for post-pandemic scenarios which could constitute a paradigm shift within higher education or a reinvention at least. Taking into consideration the lessons learned and

still remaining aware that the true benefit of e-learning within higher education could not have been experienced during the emergency response, could allow for large scale integration of permanent e-learning formats, such as blended learning. Given the proper competences and infrastructure, such a shift could also enable larger access to higher education especially in developing countries, allow for flexibility in students' schedule and with that for other engagements such as care work, family and sources of income.

3.2 Future research priorities within ide3a

Based on the findings of this literature review and calls for research on both best practice formats during emergency remote teaching and the potential of future e-learning use by several articles (n=12), we have formulated the following research priorities to be investigated within the ide3a project. First, the relationship between instructors having received support during the shift to digital formats and their intention to incorporate digital pedagogy in the future should be explored. Second, based on the findings on predicting factors of technology acceptance of some articles, and the additional generational gap between digital natives and their instructors, is there a difference between student and instructors' hopes and intentions for post-pandemic education formats? These research priorities will be examined within the ide3a project using a large scale Europe-wide survey addressed to both students and instructors. Finally, different digital best practice formats (synchronous and asynchronous formats) will be compared to blended formats and evaluated in their instructional effectiveness as well as for benefits in international short-term mobility within the ide3a project.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper we summarised the outcomes of the literature review we conducted on the impacts of COVID-19 on higher education and the research priorities we derive from them for our ongoing ide3a project. Our literature review findings largely confirm those of Aristovnik et al. [2], dated August 2020. Most data and conclusions regarding the impact of COVID-19 on higher education stems from relatively early stages of the pandemic and are largely sectoral or focus on single universities. Nonetheless, it is evident that the current emergency remote teaching formats are to be distinguished from e-learning, which has not been adopted in its full potential. The improvisational nature of the shift to digital teaching is largely due to underlying structural and institutional deficiencies in digital readiness, which have been exposed by the pandemic and present a unique chance for pedagogical reinvention. Whether digital pedagogy will remain within higher education and possibly transform teaching all together remains to be seen. Our findings are also confirmed and complemented by a recent analytical report by the European Commission [5] (published in March 2021), which formulates policy recommendations to address the challenges a continued adoption of digital education formats will pose. Within the ide3a project, we will contribute to tackle the challenge of understanding and supporting instructors in their adaptation to digital formats and safeguarding the quality of higher education experience for students.

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